

Lipid Composition of Parshey Roe (*Mugil parsia*)

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The roe lipid of parshey (*Mugil parshey*), a salt water fish belonging to the group-mullet, is found to contain high level of lipid, a large level of which is wax ester. The amount of triglycerides and phospholipids present in roe lipid is low. In total lipid, neutral lipid and phospholipid, unsaturated fatty acids of varying chain-length are present, whereas wax ester contains less unsaturated fatty acids and mostly saturated long chain alcohol. The lipid content and composition and fatty acid and alcohol composition of roe of parshey is described with the possible significance of the high content of wax ester.

The wax esters have been reported to be the major class of lipid in fish roe¹. The wax esters are found to be the dominant class of lipids in many planktonic crustaceans and has been postulated that they serve as longterm energy stores². The roe lipids of *Mugil cephalus*^{1,3} and gouramis⁴ were reported to comprise a high level of wax esters. The lipids of mullet (*Mugil cephalus*)¹ analysed in different seasons was reported to contain wax ester in roe lipid only during breeding season. The wax esters may be a phylogenetic vestige which is still prominent in *Ruvettus*⁵ and *Lati-merica*⁶ as living fossils of early vertebrate development which presumably occurs in mullet only in embryonic development.

The fatty acid composition of total lipid, neutral lipid and phospholipid and fatty acid and alcohol composition of wax ester in roe lipid have been described in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

The contents of different class of lipids is shown in Table 1. The lipid content in roe is higher than that in liver and flesh of the fish⁷. Most interesting feature of the roe lipid is its high content of wax esters. Other lipids are present in minor amounts. High level of wax ester as in *M. parsia* roe lipid has been reported in the roe lipids of *M. cephalus*¹ (a species of mullet), *Barracudina* lipid⁸ in planktons like *C. finmarchicus*⁹, in Blackbelly rose fish¹⁰, Capelin (a fish) oil¹¹, deep sea teleost fish^{12,13} in *H. atlanticus*¹⁴, midwater-rarine fish (family of *Gonostomatidae*)¹⁵. The high level of wax ester in fish is believed to be utilised as stored energy^{16,17}.

The fatty acid composition of the roe lipid (total, phospholipid and neutral lipids) are presented in Table 2 along with the corresponding hydrogenated product. In most of the cases, sum of the total unsaturated fatty acid or alcohol contents (Tables 2 and 3) in any particular chain-length is almost equal to the hydrogenated products. However in some cases noticeable differences between hydrogenated and nonhydrogenated products are found which could be explained by overlapping of some components during analysis of the nonhydrogenated products.

The presence of significance level of odd numbered fatty acids in roe lipid is interesting. High level of odd numbered fatty acids is reported in *Mugil cephalus* also¹. It is evident from the tables that low level of C₂₀ and C₂₂ polyunsaturated fatty acids are present in this lipid compared to flesh and liver lipid⁷. Also the saturated fatty acid content is higher in this lipid. In total lipid and phospholipid, fatty acid of W₆ series are less than W₃ series, whereas in the neutral lipid the W₆ and W₃ fatty acids are present almost in equal proportion. The unsaturated fatty acids of both W₆ and W₃ series have been reported in the lipid of Barramindi and golden perch eggs with the contribution of latter more than the former¹⁸. The present result of the fatty acid composition of phospholipid and neutral lipid is comparable with those in *Barracudina* lipid⁸, the only exception being the presence of high level of 14 : 0 in the latter.

The fatty acid and alcohol composition of the parshey roe wax ester is presented in Table 3 along with the hydrogenated products. It is apparent that alcohol contains saturated and monoenoic chain-length upto C₁₈ and only a trace amount of 18 : 2 W₆ is present, however the fatty acid part contain polyenoic acids upto 22 : 6 W₃. The alcohol of 14, 15 and 16 carbon-chain are present at a higher level than the corresponding acid. The contribution of C₁₆ is about 75% in alcohol while in acid it is 40%. The acid part contains very low amount of C₂₀ and C₂₂ as evident from the non-hydrogenated data analysis. From the hydrogenated product data analysis it is apparent (Table 3) that the main polyunsaturated fatty acid is 18 : 2 W₆ and 18 : 3 W₃.

TABLE 1—TOTAL LIPID CONTENT AND COMPOSITION OF DIFFERENT CLASS OF LIPIDS (%) IN PARSHEY (*Mugil parsia*) ROE

Lipid wt%	Composition of lipid (%)		
	Wax ester	Neutral lipid other than wax ester	Phospholipid
8.4 ± 0.8	67 ± 3.5	8 ± 1.2	18 ± 1.8

Lipid isolated from roe were separated into individual components by tlc and percentage of each was determined as described in the methods n = 4.

TABLE 2—FATTY ACID COMPOSITION (Wt%) OF TOTAL LIPID, PHOSPHO-LIPID AND NEUTRAL LIPID FRACTIONS OF PARSHEY (*M. parsia*) ROE*

Component	Total lipid			Phospholipid			Neutral lipid		
	NH	H	H'	NH	H	H'	NH	H	H'
14:0	2.3	2.9	2.8	1.7	1.7	1.6	7.9	8.0	7.8
15:0	0.9	2.9	2.9	2.0	2.1	1.9	2.9	3.0	3.2
16:0	28.4	36.2	37.2	36.1	43.2	43.5	26.0	53.0	52.9
16:1 W ₉	9.5			6.6			25.0		
17:0	1.8	7.0	7.2	+	1.8	2.0	5.8	5.2	5.4
17:1 W ₈	8.0			1.6			1.0		
18:0	6.5	35.8	36.0	17.0	32.0	31.6	12.4	22.0	21.8
18:1 W ₉	18.2			12.5			5.8		
18:2 W ₆	6.9			1.6			3.0		
18:3 W ₃	2.1			0.6			0.8		
18:4 W ₃	0.9			0.7			0.5		
20:0	1.1	6.5	6.7	+	11.2	12.0	2.0	5.5	5.8
20:3 W ₆	0.6			+			0.3		
20:4 W ₆	2.0			4.0			1.6		
20:5 W ₃	2.2			8.3			2.0		
22:0	+	6.5	6.3	+	7.6	7.0	+	3.2	3.0
22:5 W ₃	+			1.4			1.2		
22:6 W ₃	3.8			5.0			0.7		
<u>SFA</u>	<u>41.0</u>			<u>56.8</u>			<u>57.0</u>		
<u>UFA</u>	<u>54.2</u>	=0.76		<u>42.3</u>	=1.34		<u>41.9</u>	=1.36	
W ₆	<u>9.5</u>	=1.05		<u>5.6</u>	=0.35		<u>4.9</u>	=0.94	
W	<u>9.0</u>			<u>16.0</u>			<u>5.2</u>		

*NH = Nonhydrogenated mixed fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) analysed on DEGS column; H = hydrogenated FAME analysed on DEGS column, H' = hydrogenated FAME analysed on SE-30 column; n = 3; standard variation, 2–5%.

For further confirmation of the identification of individual fatty acid obtained from the wax esters, we fractionated the fatty acid methyl esters from wax esters on silver nitrate column chromatography¹⁹. Fraction containing definite number of unsaturation (0–6) was isolated and analysed. The composition of fatty acid present in individual fraction as well as in the whole mixture isolated from the total lipid is presented in Table 4. Except some minor variation the composition is well matched with that shown in Table 2. The ratio of SFA to UFA as well as W₆ to W₃ also remain the same after fractionation, again suggesting that our identification was quite correct. The presence of 16:2 W₆ in wax esters is interesting. Table 5 shows the hydrogenation product of all these fractions analysed on DEGS and SE-30 GLC column.

The fatty acid and alcohol composition of *M. parsia* wax ester is comparable to that of *M. cephalus*¹. The fatty acid and alcohol were reported in gouramis²⁰ and conform to the observation that their main constituents are mainly saturated and monounsaturated acids and alcohols^{12,13}. The

 TABLE 3—FATTY ACID AND ALCOHOL COMPOSITION (Wt%) OF WAX ESTER ISOLATED FROM THE ROE LIPID OF PARSHEY (*M. parsia*)*

Component	Acid			Alcohol		
	NH	H	H'	NH	H	H'
14:0	1.7	2.1	2.2	10.3	10.6	10.4
15:0	0.6	2.8	2.7	8.1	8.0	8.3
16:0	30.2	40.1	39.8	67.8	73.4	73.6
16:1 W ₉	8.3			5.3		
17:0	2.1	6.2	6.1	1.5	2.6	2.6
17:1 W ₈	5.1			1.4		
18:0	3.5	42.0	42.6	3.4	5.4	5.0
18:1 W ₉	24.4			2.0		
18:2 W ₆	10.0			0.1		
18:3 W ₃	4.2			—		
18:4 W ₃	1.6			—		
20:0	+	2.7	2.5	+	+	+
20:2 W ₆	1.0			—		
20:4 W ₆	1.0			—		
20:5 W ₃	0.5			—		
22:0	—	3.5	3.3	—	—	—
22:2 W ₆	0.6			—		
22:5 W ₆	0.3			—		
22:5 W ₃	1.0			—		
22:6 W ₃	1.6			—		
<u>SFA</u>	<u>38.1</u>	=0.64		<u>91.1</u>	=10.35	
<u>UFA</u>	<u>59.6</u>			<u>8.8</u>		
W ₆	<u>12.9</u>	=1.45				
W ₃	<u>8.9</u>					

*n = 2; other conditions are the same as in Table 2.

monoethylenic isomer distribution in the C₂₀ and C₂₂ chain-length of the alcohols parallels with the fatty acids and therefore supports the accepted view of reasonable free interconversion of acids and alcohols which is also applicable to 18:1 alcohols in elasmobranch fishes²¹. Our finding is that the fatty alcohols of wax ester lack polyunsaturated component. Biological synthesis of normal long-chain compound leads to fatty acids and it is suggestive to seem them present in alcohols due to reduction^{23,24}. If the long-chain fatty alcohols were obtained by the bio-reduction of the corresponding fatty acids, then fatty alcohols corresponding to each fatty acid should be present in the system. But in the wax ester of parshey roe lipid, only saturated alcohols of C₁₄, C₁₅, C₁₆ and C₁₈ chain-length and trace amount of unsaturated component are found, while fatty acids upto 22:6 W₆ are obtained. The presence of only a few alcohols in comparison to fatty acids may be explained by the substrate specificity in reduction as observed in rat gastrointestinal tract²⁴.

The wax esters of *M. parsia* (mullet) offers three novel features: (i) their occurrence is limited to the roe lipid, (ii)

TABLE 4—FATTY ACID COMPOSITION (Wt%) OF DIFFERENT FRACTIONS OF WAX ESTER SEPARATED ACCORDING TO THE NUMBER OF DOUBLE BONDS BY ARGENTATION CHROMATOGRAPHY ISOLATED FROM THE ROE LIPID OF PARSHEY (*M. parsia*)*

Fraction 1 Saturates wt. 26.8 mg			Fraction 2 Monoenes wt. 16.6 mg			Fraction 3 Dienes wt. 0.7 mg			Fraction 4 Trienes wt. 0.5 mg		
1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
12:0	+	+	14-9	+	+	14-6	3.6	0.4	14-3	12.2	0.1
13:0	+	+	15-8	0.9	0.3	15-5	4.7	0.5	15-5	11.2	0.1
14:0	3.2	1.4	16-9	43.7	12.6	16-6	10.0	1.1	16-3	50.0	0.4
15:0	1.3	0.6	17-8	1.5	0.4	17-5	2.1	0.2	18-3	26.4	0.2
16:0	81.9	36.2	18-9	52.9	15.4	18-6	66.5	7.6	19-5	+	+
17:0	4.8	2.1	19-8	+	+	19-5	+	+	20-3	+	+
18:0	9.0	3.9	20-9	0.5	0.1	20-6	3.0	0.4			
19:0	+	+	22-9	1.0	0.3	22-6	10.1	1.9			
20:0	+	+									

Fraction 5 Tetraene wt. 1.6 mg			Fraction 6 Pentaene wt. 7.4 mg			Fraction 7 Hexaene wt. 0.5 mg			SFA	W ₆
1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	UFA	W ₃
16-4	4.1	0.1	18-3	4.7	0.6	22-3	99.8	0.8	44.0	11.7
16-1	43.1	1.1	19-2	2.9	0.3				56.0	11.7
17-5	8.5	0.1	20-3	28.2	3.4				= 0.74	= 1.0
17-2	8.6	0.2	21-5	10.7	1.1					
18-3	30.2	0.8	22-6	5.2	0.6					
19-5	+	+	22-3	48.0	5.4					
20-6	4.0	0.1								

*Column 1 represents the chain-length and carbon end chain, e.g. in fraction 2, 18-9 represents 18 : 1W₉, i.e. a monoene with 18 carbon chain in which the carbon end chain (number of carbon atoms beyond the double bond furthest from carboxyl end) is 9; Column 2 represents the percentage of the component acid in a particular fraction; Column 3 represents the percentage of the acids in the whole mixture computed from the percentage of the fraction, n = 2.

they contain mostly saturated and monounsaturated alcohols and (iii) they have significant level of odd numbered fatty acids and alcohols. The wax esters may be a phylogenetic vestige which is still prominent in *Ruvettus* and *Latimeria* as living fossils of early vertebrate development and which may occur in mullet only in embryonic development.

Experimental

Fresh fish were purchased from the local market in July and August, i.e. during breeding season. They were divided into four to five batches. Roe was carefully separated, cleaned, weighed and lipids were isolated²⁵. The lipid was dried under nitrogen, weighed and stored under nitrogen at - 20° for further analysis.

The roe lipids isolated above were separated into wax esters, neutral lipid and phospholipid by silicic acid column chromatography²⁶. The quantification of neutral lipid and wax ester were made by direct weighing and phospholipid by colorimetric method²⁷.

Isolation and esterification of fatty acids : The neutral and phospholipid were treated with potassium methoxide for simultaneous liberation and esterification of fatty acids²⁸, and fatty acid composition in the form of methyl esters were determined by glc analysis. An aliquot was hydrogenated⁴ and again analysed by glc.

Identification and characterisation : Wax ester was saponified with methanolic potassium hydroxide. Alcohol and the potassium salt of fatty acids were isolated as described⁴. The free acids were liberated from potassium salt on acidification with 4 N H₂SO₄ which were then esterified with boron trifluoride-methanol²⁹ for glc analysis. Alcohol was converted to acetates with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine³⁰. The purity of the acetates was

TABLE 5—FATTY ACID COMPOSITION (Wt%) OF THE HYDROGENATED PRODUCTS OF DIFFERENT FRACTION OF WAX ESTER SEPARATED BY ARGENTATION COLUMN CHROMATOGRAPHY ACCORDING TO THE NUMBER OF DOUBLE BONDS FROM ROE LIPID OF PARSHEY (*M. parsia*)*

a	Fraction 1 Saturates		Fraction 2 Saturates		Fraction 3 Saturates		Fraction 4 Saturates		Fraction 5 Saturates		Fraction 6 Saturates		Fraction 7 Saturates	
	b	c	b	c	b	c	b	c	b	c	b	c	b	c
12	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	3.3	3.1	+	+	3.2	3.3	12.1	12.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.2	4.7	4.6	11.5	11.5	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	81.8	82.4	45.7	45.3	12.6	12.8	50.0	50.3	51.2	52.5	-	-	-	-
17	4.9	4.8	3.3	3.6	2.0	2.2	-	-	6.7	6.3	-	-	-	-
18	8.8	8.5	48.3	48.1	67.5	67.0	23.9	23.6	35.8	35.2	4.6	4.4	-	-
19	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	1.1	0.9	2.9	2.7	-	-
20	+	+	0.6	0.5	+	+	0.1	0.1	4.0	4.2	28.1	28.3	-	-
21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.0	9.7	-	-
22	-	-	0.8	0.9	9.7	9.8	-	-	-	-	53.5	53.3	99.5	99.7

*a = Carbon chain-length; b = glc analysis on 10% DEGS column; c = glc analysis on SE-30 column; n = 2.

checked by tlc and composition and quantification were made by glc analysis. The methyl esters were subjected to argentation column chromatography for separation of FAME mixtures according to their double bonds¹⁹ followed by glc analysis. Both fatty acid methyl esters and acetates were hydrogenated³¹ and again analysed by glc.

Glc was performed with a F & M 700-R chromatograph. Columns used were 15% DEGS and 5% SE-30, both coated on 100–200 mesh Gas chrome P and packed respectively into 6 × 1/8 and 6 × 1/4 inch in stainless tubings. The liquid phases and support were obtained from Applied Science Laboratories (U.S.A.). Nitrogen at 25 lb/inch² pressure was used as carrier gas. The flow rate was kept at 40 ml/min. The operating column temperature was 160 and 180° respectively, for DEGS and SE-30.

The peaks were identified using (i) cod-liver oil fatty acid methyl esters as secondary standard³², (ii) semi-logarithmic plots³³ of relative retention time against carbon chain-length of fatty acids of cod-liver oil³⁴, and finding the log of relative retention time of the fatty acid under investigation into these plots, (iii) chromatograms of the corresponding hydrogenated products.

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